

Effects of voice assistant recommendations on consumer behaviour

Abstract

The present study compares the influence of text-based recommendations; traditionally known as online consumer reviews, and the influence of voice-based recommendations provided by voice-driven virtual assistants on consumer behaviours. Based on media richness theory, the research model investigates how voice vs. text modality influences consumers' perceptions of credibility and usefulness, as well as their behavioural intentions and actual behaviours. In addition, the study analyses if these relationships vary based on the type of product and compares the influence of masculine and feminine voices. Two studies were conducted using between-subjects experimental designs, PLS-SEM and logistic regression. The core finding is that voice-based recommendations are more effective than online consumer reviews in altering consumer behaviours. In addition, the first study showed that the influence of recommendations on behavioural intentions is mediated by consumers' perceptions of their credibility and usefulness. The second study confirmed, in a realistic setting, that voice-based recommendations affect consumer choices to a greater extent. Recommendations for search products and provided by males are also found to be more effective. These results contribute to the voice assistant and e-WOM literature by highlighting the effectiveness of voice-based recommendations in predicting consumer behaviours, confirming that credibility and usefulness are key factors that determine the influence of recommendations, and showing that recommendations are more effective when they focus on search products.

Keywords

e-WOM, Recommendations, Voice assistant, Online consumer review, Virtual assistant, Artificial Intelligence, Consumer behaviour.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) technologies have become deeply embedded in, and substantially changed, every aspect of modern life. Among the fastest growing categories of AI technologies are virtual assistants (Ahn, 2022). Virtual assistants have been described as dialogue systems, often displaying human-like behaviours, that interact with their users to perform tasks, support interfaces that adapt to users' queries, and as personal agents that proactively support their users, modelling their needs (Bräuer and Mazarakis, 2022).

Based on their input modality, virtual assistants have been segmented into chatbots and voice assistants (Foster and Oberlander, 2007). A chatbot is a computer program that carries out textual conversations (Pizzi et al., 2021), whereas voice assistant is a device, powered by AI, usually integrated as software into various platforms (e.g., smartphones, TVs) and Bluetooth speakers (e.g., Amazon Echo, Alexa), that listen out for wake-up words (i.e., 'Alexa...' or 'Hey Google...') which activate their functionality. When the device detects its user wake-up word, its software understands what is being said and provides a response in real time (Grover et al., 2020). Voice assistants give advice based on consumers' preferences and habits, to which they have access (Ling et al., 2021). This feature, advice-based consumer preferences, guides consumers during their purchase decision-making processes by providing product/service recommendations.

While the market of voice assistants is still young, the penetration levels of voice-enabled technologies are growing exponentially. The growth of the voice assistant industry is expected to average 28% per year between 2021 and 2023 (Statista, 2021). In addition, forecasts suggest that, by 2023, the number of voice assistants (including integrated software and Bluetooth speakers) will surpass 8.4 billion units - a number greater than the world's population (Statista, 2021). More than one-third of the US population use voice assistants (115.2 million users in 2019, with a predicted 135.6 million users by the end of 2022), millennials being the heaviest users, but use is rising among all age groups (Petrock, 2020). In addition, 70% of Google Assistant requests are voice-based, and 43% of these requests seek product recommendations when ordering items (ComScore, 2021). In the hospitality context, a recent research that surveyed 16,000 travellers from 25 countries suggests that half of the respondents use voice search for some part of their trip (Global Digital Traveler Research Report, 2021).

Thus, voice assistants have emerged as a new recommendation system for consumers, complementing e-WOM, which itself changed the buying environment following the advent of Web 2.0 (Verma and Yadav, 2021). E-WOM has been found to be the most influential online

information source in shaping consumer behaviours (Cantallops and Salvi, 2014; Filieri and McLeay, 2014), as its readers tend to perceive it as more reliable due to the poster's independence (Casaló et al., 2010; Park and Lee, 2009). E-WOM has been defined as “any positive or negative statement made by potential, actual, or former customers about a product or company, which is made available to a multitude of people and institutions via the Internet” (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004, p. 39). Online consumer reviews are the most common form of e-WOM (Chatterjee, 2001), and are a crucial source of information for other consumers, who use them to assess products and services before purchasing them (Filieri, 2016). Specifically, online consumer reviews are text-based declarations posted on websites that host consumer reviews (Filieri et al., 2018a). Voice assistants have been shown to provide benefits over and above those provided by e-WOM by giving consumers personalised product recommendations based on their needs, which they have inferred from their conversations with their users (Tabassum et al., 2019). As a result, academic research has emphasised the high importance of voice assistants in terms of the future of e-WOM for companies (e.g., hotels/restaurants) and their product promotion potential (Klaus and Zaichkowsky, 2020; Hernandez-Ortega and Ferreira, 2021).

The current study responds to the call for further empirical research on the influence of voice assistants on consumer behaviour proposed by recent systematic literature reviews (e.g., Lim et al., 2022; Ling et al., 2021). These works mainly highlight factors influencing the consumer intention to use AI and voice assistants as well as their applications in marketing field. Also, this research extends existing empirical works on voice assistants in the consumer behaviour domain, which have mainly focused on analysing consumers' perceptions and behaviours towards voice assistants (e.g., engagement and loyalty [Moriuchi, 2019] love [Hernandez-Ortega and Ferreira, 2021], or trust [Balakrishnan and Dwivedi, 2021; Pitardi and Marriot, 2021]), by drawing attention to the potential influence of voice assistants recommendations about other products/services on consumer choices.

Specifically, some prior literature review papers seem to suggest that AI-based devices such as virtual assistants may have a strong effect on consumers' choices, being able to alter their preferences as a result of AI-based interactions (e.g., Mariani et al., 2021; Klaus and Zaichkowsky, 2020). Using a voice assistant can be a unique experience, distinct from other recommendation-offering technologies (Lieberman and Schroeder 2020). Voice assistants' ability to convey warmth, and to make their listeners feel in control, and competent (e.g., through the provision of immediate answers through natural language processing), enhance the perceived quality of their recommendations (Dellaert et al., 2020). Nevertheless, according to Bjork (1970, voice information subsists on a single temporal dimension, so that people have difficulties

retaining vocal information in their short-term memories, while visual memory is more relied upon for information stored in our long-term memory. Klaus and Zaichkowsky (2020) adopted this concept to voice assistants, suggesting that, when people ask a voice assistant for a recommendation for a product/service, and they reject the first recommendation, the assistant makes a second, and a third, and so on. However, people are unlikely to ask for a fourth option and, if they do, they will have difficulty comparing it to the first option, which they have already started to forget. Accepting the first recommendation that voice assistants make is, thus, usual. Therefore, Dellaert et al. (2020) suggested that voice assistants indirectly limit the amount of information provided to consumers. On the other hand, text-based recommendations (e.g., online consumer reviews) provide several options which can be simultaneously presented on a screen and remain frozen there for a span of time. Therefore, receiving information from online platforms leads consumers to retain their role as decision-makers (Klaus and Zaichkowsky, 2020). However, extant studies do not seem fully able to explain the influence of voice assistants' recommendations on consumers' perceptions and intentions or compare the influence they exert with that exerted by other recommendation sources, such as online consumer reviews. The previous research into voice assistants has focused on other aspects, such as their design and functional properties (e.g., Sciuto et al., 2018), their anthropomorphism and social functions (e.g., Schweitzer et al., 2019), customers' attitudes towards them (e.g., Brill et al., 2019) and the personalisation-privacy paradox (e.g., Lau et al., 2018). While some comparative studies have been undertaken in this context, for example, synthetic vs. the human voice (Cherif and Lemoine., 2019), customer satisfaction in voice commerce vs. e-commerce (Kraus, 2019) and voice mail vs. e-email (Keil and Johnson, 2002), no studies have compared the effectiveness of text-based recommendations (online consumer reviews) and the voice-based recommendations provided by voice assistants.

Previous research has extensively examined the effectiveness of e-WOM reviews by assessing review credibility and usefulness (Cheung et al., 2009; Filieri et al., 2020), perceived helpfulness (Filieri et al., 2018b; Filieri, 2015), perceived competence (Lim and Van der Heide, 2015), relevance, factuality, source credibility and ranking score (Filieri et al., 2018a), length, valence, argument quality and content equivocality (Cheng and Ho, 2015; Filieri, 2015; Schindler and Bickart, 2012). Of these factors the prior research highlighted the vital roles of credibility and usefulness in the persuasiveness of e-WOM; they have both been found to influence consumers' intentions and behaviours (Cheung et al., 2008; Cheung et al., 2009; Filieri, 2015; Viglia et al., 2016). In the online review context, credibility has been defined as the "consumers' perception that the information contained in a review is 'believable, true, or factual'" (Cheung et al., 2009,

p. 12). The usefulness of online reviews has been defined as “the degree to which consumers believe that online reviews would facilitate their purchase decision-making process” (Park and Lee, 2009, p. 334). Therefore, taking into account that these two factors are crucial in the determination of the influence of recommendations, it is proposed that the contribution of the present study to the literature is threefold. First, we compare the influence on consumer behaviour of text-based recommendations received through online consumer reviews and through voice assistants’ recommendations. Second, we analyse the mediating role of the key perceptions (credibility, usefulness) that users develop during the process. Third, the moderating effect of product type (search vs. experience) is examined to better understand if relationships vary based on whether a product or service is being recommended.

Our theoretical approach is based on media richness theory (MRT), which proposes that communication channels have affordances that influence consumers’ perceptions and intentions. The theory was introduced by Daft and Lengel (1986) and was subsequently applied to the new media that emerged in the 1990s (e.g., email) and the 2000s (e.g., social media). The concept of media richness (Daft and Lengel, 1986) offers a theoretical framework for analysing the possible advantages that consumers may derive from different forms of media.

Empirically, we performed two experimental studies. The first analysed the influence of the recommendation mode employed (text vs. voice) on the users’ key perceptions (credibility, usefulness); the mode used may affect consumers’ behavioural intentions (i.e., intention to follow the recommendation, intention to recommend and intention to purchase). The second experiment aimed to enhance the realism of the scenario by measuring actual behaviours, rather than intentions –and hence the external validity and generalisability of the results– following the design recommendations of Viglia et al. (2021). To confirm the influence of the recommendation mode (text vs. voice) on behaviour, we presented the experimental participants with a situation in which they had to make choices, controlling for the apparent gender of the voice assistant (i.e., masculine vs. feminine voice).

The key result of the study is that voice assistants’ recommendations are more effective than online consumer reviews in influencing consumer behaviours, both directly –Study 2– and indirectly (via credibility and usefulness) –Study 1–. These findings give professionals a deep grasp of voice assistant technologies that they may use to their advantage in business strategies.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Media Richness Theory and the influence of recommendation modality on perceived credibility and usefulness

Communication channels have different attributes that affect consumers' perceptions and intentions. The most important is modality (Berger and Iyengar, 2013). MRT was originally posited to explain the effects of different types of media on task performance. The theory's core proposition is that the more cues a communication channel features, that is, the "richer" the medium is, the more satisfying and effective it will be perceived (Daft and Lengel, 1986; Caplan et al., 2014). Face-to-face interaction has been classified as the "richest" way to communicate because it transmits verbal and non-verbal cues, which mitigate misunderstandings, whereas unaddressed documents (e.g., standard reports) have been described as the medium with the least communication richness (Campbell, 2006). Below we apply MRT to compare the influence of voice assistants' recommendations and e-WOM recommendations (in the form of text-based online reviews) on consumers' perceptions and intentions.

In general, AI-based devices (e.g., robots, virtual assistants) try to interact by using human-like features that elicit positive responses from users (Scheepers et al., 2022; Belanche et al., 2021; Ahn, 2022). In particular, voice assistants use their voice function to relay information. This voice function is an important human-like characteristic that evokes a sense of social presence in the mind of consumers, which prompts them to interact with the voice assistant in the same way they would socially interact with humans (e.g., Rosenthal-von der Pütten et al., 2016). In addition, as individuals become comfortable in their conversations with voice assistants, they start to build rapport with the devices, just as they would in their personal relationships (Rhee and Choi, 2020; Moriuchi, 2019). Prior studies have shown that the voice feature leads users to personify voice assistants (Tassiello et al., 2021), and even consider them as friends or family members (Zhao and Rau, 2020). Similarly, several researchers have suggested that voice assistants make experiences more intimate, humanise interactions and enhance trust between the consumer and the service (Qiu and Benbasat, 2009). In addition, Ostrom et al. (2019) argued that voice assistants make consumers more effective, as they offer convenience and speed (Klaus and Zaichkowsky, 2020). According to Rosenthal-von der Pütten et al. (2019), consumers feel it is often easier and more convenient to use voice input than to type, as voice is regarded as faster. In addition, Rhee and Choi (2020) found that personalisation is the main advantage of voice assistants. Voice assistants give recommendations based on consumers' histories, preferences and habits, to which they have access through algorithm-based systems. Thus, consumers receive personalised recommendations which provide appropriate information, increasing the effectiveness of the recommendations which, consequently, facilitate their purchase decision-

making processes. Invitational rhetoric" is the degree to which a communication style encourages others to converse; a higher degree fosters mutual understanding (Liu and Sundar, 2018). Kontogiorgos et al. (2019) analysed the effects of the invitational rhetoric in both chatbots and voice assistants' messages, and found that the latter's messages contained invitational rhetoric which had a beneficial effect on users' perceptions and behavioural outcomes.

On the other hand, in the context of text-based recommendations, various scholars have argued that many consumer reviews posted on online platforms fail to meet users' needs. Listeners are more attentive and responsive to devices with high non-verbal contingency and expressive narrative styles (e.g., in terms of pitch and tone [Kory Westlund et al., 2017]). Text-based recommendations contain less cues than voice-based recommendations, which can convey information with non-verbal cues such as voice tone, speed, pitch, volume and emphasis (Kontogiorgos et al., 2019). For example, Stoll et al. (2016) and Spence et al. (2019) found that consumers feel more uncertainty and expect fewer positive experiences when they read text-based recommendations. These findings align with the main MRT proposition, that is, when a technology exhibits human traits (e.g., voice) and elicits human-like interactions, people's responses to the technology will mirror social behaviours and they will respond to it consistent with social standards, as in their personal interactions (Moon and Nass, 1996). Therefore, voice assistants may be considered to be a rich communication channel (Rudovic et al., 2018).

Taking these points, and MRT, into account, their voice features, natural-language processing and immediate feedback make voice assistants a rich communication channel, leading consumers to consider them as friends/conversational partners. As a result, a personal acquaintance and trusting relationship can develop (Pitardi and Marriott, 2021). The more familiarity the message recipient has with the sender (e.g., a friend), the more reliable the information in the message is regarded (Keller, 2007; Bampo et al., 2008). On the other hand, the multiple cues that voice assistants transmit increase the accuracy of the data they impart (e.g., detailed information about a product/service), which can alleviate uncertainty, resolve ambiguity and help consumers acquire the information they need. Hence, they may be perceived as more useful (Filiari, 2015). Therefore, we hypothesise that:

H1. Voice recommendations (vs. text recommendations) generate higher levels of (a) perceived credibility and (b) perceived usefulness.

2.2 The influence of recommendation credibility on the perceived usefulness of recommendations

Several works examining online reviews have stressed the importance of source credibility (e.g., Filieri, 2015; Lo and Yao, 2019) over message credibility. However, message credibility may also have a crucial role in the evaluation of reviews; it has been defined as “the consumers’ perception that the information contained in a review is believable, true, or factual” (Cheung et al., 2009, p. 12). In this respect, scholars usually agree that perceived credibility enhances the perceived helpfulness and effectiveness of information (Filieri et al., 2018b, Kamins et al., 1989). When a recommendation is considered credible, the information it contains is perceived as accurate and reliable and, thus, useful for the consumer’s decision-making. Indeed, online reviews that consumers perceive to be useful provide them with diagnostic information pre-purchase that enable them to better assess the quality of products and how they are likely to perform; that is, perceptions of usefulness make the message more effective (Filieri, 2015). Thus, we argue that if consumers regard a recommendation as credible, they are highly likely to consider the recommendation to be useful. The following hypothesis is proposed:

H2. The perceived credibility of a recommendation has a positive effect on its perceived usefulness.

2.3 The influence of perceived credibility and usefulness on behavioural intentions

Behavioural intentions reflect the strength of a person’s willingness to perform a specific behaviour; the stronger the intention to conduct the behaviour, the more likely it is that the behaviour will be conducted (Ajzen, 1991). Intention to follow recommendations, intention to purchase and intention to recommend are the most important consumer behavioural intentions related to recommended products, as they provide solid explanations of how the consumer will behave in the future (Casaló et al., 2011; Cheung and Thadani, 2012).

Scholars have demonstrated that perceived message credibility is one of the most important antecedents of recommendation adoption (Cheung et al., 2009) and purchase intentions (Filieri, 2016). Credibility is determined early in the information persuasion process (Wathen and Burkell, 2002). When consumers establish that a recommendation has credibility, they regard the information it contains as clear and their confidence in accepting it increases (Petty et al., 2002; Sussman and Siegal, 2003). By contrast, if a recommendation is judged to be untrustworthy, consumers lose confidence in the source’s intentions because of their distrust, and the message has reduced persuasiveness (Teng et al., 2014). Thus, credibility positively affects the consumer’s intention to follow recommendations (Zhang et al., 2014) and the probability that the recommendation will be used in his/her purchase decision (Lis and Post, 2013). Finally, when consumers receive a credible product/service recommendation, they put trust in it, and perceive

it to provide valid information about the product/service, which leads them to consider it important for their personal contacts, and to recommend it to them. This is consistent with previous research into consumers' behavioural intentions to share information on consumer online platforms (Filieri et al., 2020; Filieri 2015; Ma and Chan, 2014). In sum, perceived credibility is an important factor in making recommendations more persuasive and for increasing consumers' behavioural intentions. As a consequence, we propose:

H3. The perceived credibility of a recommendation has a positive effect on consumers' behavioural intentions: (a) to follow the recommendation; (b) to purchase the product/service; and (c) to recommend the product/service.

Similarly, Filieri (2015) and Cheung et al. (2008) suggested that usefulness is the primary factor in consumers' evaluations of recommendations and is an effective predictor of their intentions. In the online review context, when useful information is provided in a recommendation, this increases consumers' knowledge of, and familiarity with, the product/service (Cheung et al., 2008; Filieri, 2015). Hence, useful recommendations are particularly influential in consumers' decision-making as they affect their information adoption and purchase intentions (Filieri et al., 2018a, 2018b). Thus, only those reviews that their readers perceive as useful have been found to affect intention formation through the impression they create about the subject of the review (Purnawirawan et al., 2012). In addition, consumers have been shown to be more likely to share information contained in a review with others if they perceive the recommendations it contains to be useful (Park and Lee 2009). Consumers share information, or form intention to recommend a product/service, because they want to help other people make good decisions about what they buy and/or avoid bad experiences (Chiu et al. 2009). Consequently:

H4. The perceived usefulness of a recommendation has a positive effect on consumers' behavioural intentions: (a) to follow the recommendation; (b) to purchase the product/service; and (c) to recommend the product/service.

2.4 The moderating effect of product type: search vs. experience products

Nelson (1970) posited that the key difference between search and experience products is whether consumers can assess them prior to purchase. If a product's qualities can be determined prior to purchase (e.g. tangible products), it is classified as a search product; however, if a product's attributes cannot be determined until after the consumer buys and uses the product, it is classified as an experience product (e.g., a service) (Klein, 1998). Similarly, Weathers et al. (2007) categorised products into search and experience based on the degree to which consumers

believe they must use them to assess their quality. The more one's senses are required to evaluate a product; the more experience features the product contains. On the other hand, the more one believes that information will suffice to assess a product, the more search features the product contains. Several academics have hypothesised that product type may influence how consumers evaluate recommendations (e.g., Jiménez and Mendoza, 2013; Zhang et al., 2014).

As aforementioned, information on the characteristics of search products is readily available (Hsieh et al., 2005), objective, easily comparable (Mudambi and Schuff, 2010) and discoverable without experiencing the product (Huang et al., 2009). In contrast, information about experience products is difficult and costly to obtain (Mudambi and Schuff, 2010), and consumers must use their senses more to assess them (Weathers et al., 2007). In addition, as consumers cannot completely evaluate experience goods until after consumption, the risk/uncertainty associated with the choice process is greater for experience products than for search products. Risk theory (Dowling and Staelin, 1994) posits that consumers look for more information when they perceive that the decision context involves greater risk. Therefore, the associated information processing requires more cognitive effort (Huang et al., 2009). On the other hand, when information is received from a rich media source, it tends to be easier to process, interpret and assimilate, which enables consumers to better evaluate it (Maity et al., 2018 ; Suh, 1999). Therefore, when they come from rich media sources, recommendations for experience products may be easier to evaluate; as a result, the influence of voice (vs. text) recommendations in terms of the development of perceptions of credibility and usefulness will be greater for experience than for search products. Hence, we propose our last hypotheses:

H5. The difference between the (a) perceived credibility and (b) perceived usefulness of voice and text recommendations will be greater for experience products than for search products.

Figure 1. Proposed conceptual model

Note: Solid lines denote direct effects, dotted lines denote moderating effects.

3. STUDY 1

3.1 Methodology

3.1.1 Experimental design and measures

To test the proposed model, we conducted a between-subjects factorial experiment design. Specifically, we manipulated modality (voice-recommendation vs. text-recommendation) and product type (search product vs. experience product), resulting in a two-by-two factorial design that combines two variables, each of which has two levels. The participants were randomly assigned to one of four scenarios. In the current market, several voice assistants are integrated into Bluetooth speakers, such as Amazon Echo (Alexa), and as software integrated into smart devices, for example, Apple Siri. In the present study we used Amazon Echo (Alexa), because it is the leading, global smart speaker, having a market share of 30%, and 70% in the US (Statista, 2022). To simulate the experience of receiving a voice recommendation, we used a text-to-speech (TTS) demo version, accessible online at <https://tsdemo.com/>. To control for the impact of vocal features (e.g., gender, pitch, speed), we used the same female voice character, with a pre-set standard vocal effect, for all the voice recommendations. Two distinct product categories were chosen, a suitcase for the search product condition, and a dinner at a restaurant for the experience product condition.

Thereafter, the participants were asked to complete a questionnaire to allow the researchers to evaluate their perceptions of, and intentions developed based on, the recommendations received. The survey clearly identified the purpose of the research. Responses that were filled in very quickly or that failed screening questions, indicating that the participants had not paid attention to

the questions, were excluded. In the text recommendation surveys, the participants could read the recommendation. For the voice recommendation surveys, the questionnaire provided a link to an audio file on which the participant (having pressed “play”) could listen to the recommendation (see Appendixes A and B).

The variables credibility, usefulness and behavioural intentions were measured using multiple-item measurement scales on 7-point Likert-type response formats. The respondents rated the items from 1 (“strongly disagree”) to 7 (“strongly agree”). The measurement scales were adapted from scales developed in the previous literature (see Table 3).

3.1.2 Manipulation checks

Before the main experiment, a pre-test was carried out to ensure the effectiveness of the manipulations. The pre-test was conducted with 40 participants, 10 per condition. The treatment conditions were found to have been appropriately manipulated. The modality manipulation was successfully confirmed, with 98% of the participants verifying the text condition, and 99% the voice condition. The product type manipulation was also verified, 100% of the participants confirming the search product condition, and 92% the experience product condition (see Appendix C1). In addition, we controlled for realism (i.e., both real behaviours and intentions were measured), the level of consumer involvement (whether the product categories are high- or low-involvement), review characteristics (length, valence and quality) and the participants’ brand familiarity with the product/service. The measures for the realism scenario were taken from Bagozzi et al. (2016), and the measures for product/service involvement from Zaichkowsky (1985). These measures were recorded on seven-point Likert-type scales (1 = “strongly disagree”; 7 = “strongly agree”; see Appendix D). The measures of recommendation valence and length, review quality and brand familiarity were recorded on five-point Likert-type scales (1 = “Very low”; 5 = “Very high”). No statistical differences between the means were observed across the realism scenarios for user involvement, valence, length, recommendation quality or brand familiarity with the product/service (FR=1.4, $p>0.1$; FI=2.53, $p>0.1$; FV=0.93, $p>0.1$; FL=1.30, $p>0.1$; FQ=1.17, $p>0.1$); this indicates that these variables are homogeneous in all the conditions (see Appendix C2).

3.1.3 Product type

A suitcase was chosen as it is a necessary product that most people take on their travels. In addition, it can be used for a long time once purchased. Before purchasing a suitcase, people actively seek out and compare models and features. Conversely, a dinner at a restaurant is an experience product, the quality of which cannot be determined prior to interaction with the

product (i.e., eating at the restaurant). Moreover, one’s assessment of a restaurant’s quality is influenced by one’s tastes and personal interests, thus it is difficult to compare one establishment with another, or evaluate them without eating in them. In addition, the two products were chosen because they are generally in the same price range.

According to Filieri and McLeay (2014), e-WOM has a great influence on consumer purchasing decisions for high-involvement travel related products; consumers frequently spend significant time searching for information about high-involvement products so that they make the best choices (Zaichkowsky, 1986). Therefore, in the present study, we used high-involvement products. For the search product, the participants were encouraged to imagine they were purchasing a suitcase for a trip to meet their partners’ parents for the first time, and that they wanted to highly impress their future in-laws. So, they should buy a new, appropriate suitcase. For the experience product the participants were asked to imagine that were looking for a restaurant to surprise their partner, where they would invite her/him to a romantic dinner to celebrate their anniversary. Thus, they needed to book a table.

Table 1. Description of the recommendations used in the research, based on product type

Search product	Experience product
<p><i>“Last week, I bought a C.K.L suitcase. I can honestly say the design of the C.K.L suitcase and its easy handling are great. The suitcase is very spacious and elegant. The size is perfect! With pockets and multi-compartments for socks, chargers...etc. Regarding the wheel manoeuvrability, the suitcase has innovative 360-degree spinner wheels. It has an affordable price.</i></p> <p><i>I highly recommend it!</i></p> <p><i>I rate it with 4.8 out of 5 stars!”</i></p>	<p><i>“Last week I went to Summer House restaurant. I can honestly say the location of the Summer House restaurant and the service you will receive are great. The restaurant is very spacious and cosy. The location is perfect! Within walking distance to downtown. Concerning the menu, Summer House restaurant offers delicious dishes and cocktails at very reasonable prices.</i></p> <p><i>I highly recommend it!</i></p> <p><i>I rate it with 4.8 out of 5 stars!”</i></p>

3.1.4 Data collection and estimation procedure

The data collection took place during November 2021. The participants were US residents recruited through an online survey; we enlisted the assistance of a market research firm, Prolific, in the process. To take part, the participants had to have used voice assistants at least once; a qualifier sentence asked; “This survey is exclusively addressed to voice assistant users, so if you have used a voice assistant at least once, please answer this questionnaire truthfully”. Some 130

voice assistant users were recruited to undertake the survey (>30 participants per scenario). Table 2 shows the main demographic characteristics of the sample.

The data collected were analysed through partial least squares-structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM), with SMARTPLS 3.0 software, a method widely employed in recent studies (e.g., Hu et al., 2021, Ringle and Sarstedt, 2016). We selected the PLS-SEM approach because it has strong ability to model latent constructs under conditions of non-normality and places less restrictive demands on sample size and residual distribution (Chin, 1998), and because it is especially effective when a cause-effect model is exploratory in nature and reveals unique associations not previously examined in empirical studies (Hair et al., 2014). This matches our case, as we compare consumer perceptions and behavioural intentions in the context of voice vs. text recommendations.

Table 2. Demographic characteristics of the sample

		Frequency	%
Gender	Male	68	52.3
	Female	62	47.7
Age	18-25	50	38.5
	26-30	27	20.8
	31-35	19	14.6
	36-40	17	13,1
	41-45	7	5.4
	46-50	5	3.8
	51-55	4	3.1
	56-60	1	0.8
	Education level	High/Secondary school diploma	28
Undergraduate degree		76	58.5
Graduate degree		26	20.3
Citizenship	USA	122	93.8
	Other	8	6.2

3.2 Results

3.2.1 Measurement model

To evaluate the dimensional structure of the scales we first examined the factor loadings to provide an initial assessment of the constructs' internal consistency. As shown in Table 3, the factor loadings in their respective constructions exceeded the 0.7 threshold (Henseler et al., 2009). The composite reliability (CR) method was used to assess the reliability of the measurements. Table 3 shows the CR values, which surpass the suggested limit of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2014). The Cronbach's α values, similarly, were above the recommended 0.7 level for all reflective constructs (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). Convergent validity was evaluated using average variance extracted (AVE), which should be greater than 0.5 (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). The results in Table 3 show this criterion was met. Finally, the results in Table 4 validate the discriminant validity, as the square roots of the AVEs of each construct were higher than their corresponding inter-construct correlations (Fornell and Larcker, 1981).

Table 3. Reliability and validity indices

Construct	Factor loadings	Cronbach's α	CR	AVE
Usefulness (Adapted from Venkatesh, 2003, and Chang et al., 2016).		0.956	0.968	0.884
USF.1 I find the recommendation very helpful.	0.957			
USF.2 I find the recommendation very useful.	0.955			
USF.3 I find the recommendation very informative.	0.909			
USF.4 The recommendation gave me the information I needed.	0.940			
Credibility (Adapted from Meyer, 1988 and Filieri, 2015).		0.947	.962	0.862
CRD.1 I find the recommendation fair.	0.938			
CRD.2 I find the recommendation accurate.	0.894			
CRD.3 I find the recommendation credible.	0.946			
CRD.4 The arguments in the recommendation are convincing.	0.936			
Intention to follow (Adapted from Casaló et al., 2011 and Cheung et al., 2009).		0.951	0.965	0.873
IF.1 I feel comfortable behaving according to the recommendation I obtained from the voice assistant/online review.	0.943			
IF.2 I do NOT hesitate to take into account the recommendation obtained from the voice assistant/online review.	0.884			
IF.3 I feel secure in following the recommendation obtained from the voice assistant/online review	0.966			
IF.4 I will definitely follow the recommendation obtained from the voice assistant/online review.	0.940			
Intention to purchase (Adapted from Filieri et al., 2018).		0.920	0.950	0.863
IP.1 It is very likely that I would buy/choose the recommended suitcase/restaurant	0.966			
IP.2 I would definitely purchase/choose the recommended suitcase/restaurant	0.921			
IP.3 I would consider purchasing/choosing the recommended suitcase/restaurant	0.899			
Intention to recommend (Adapted from Hosany and Witham, 2010).		0.917	0.948	0.860
IR.1 I would recommend the suitcase/restaurant to friends and relatives	0.963			
IR.2 I would say positive things about the suitcase/restaurant to other people	0.948			
IR.3 I would seldom miss an opportunity to tell others about the suitcase/restaurant	0.868			
Voice modality	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Table 4. Discriminant validity

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Credibility (1)	0.929					
Intention to follow (2)	0.824	0.934				
Intention to purchase (3)	0.796	0.882	0.929			
Intention to recommend (4)	0.706	0.800	0.835	0.927		
Usefulness (5)	0.843	0.797	0.775	0.719	0.940	
Modality (6)	0.168	0.067	0.019	-0.049	0.176	1.000

Note: Diagonal elements (in **bold**) are the squared roots of the AVEs (the variance shared between the constructs and their measures). The inter-construct correlations are the off-diagonal elements.

Finally, as we collected data using a questionnaire, common method variance (CMV) was assessed; CMV may arise when respondents fill out questionnaires very quickly, in a more or less automatic manner (Podsakoff et al., 2003). In addition to the recommended procedural steps taken during the survey design and administration process (e.g., the participants were assured of anonymity and confidentiality), a single factor Harman's test was performed to test for CMV. The results indicated that no one general factor accounted for the majority of the variance, as CMV accounted for less than 50% of the variance (Baumgartner et al., 2021).

3.2.2. *Structural model*

To confirm the quality of the experimental design of the structural model, we performed the same manipulation checks as used in the pre-test. The results were again satisfactory, the scenarios were clearly understood, as were the questionnaire items. Having confirmed the appropriateness of the manipulation checks and the reliability and validity of the measurement scales, we then used PLS to assess the research model. The path relationships and R2 values of the endogenous latent variables were analysed, and the statistical significances of the path relationships were assessed using a bootstrapping process with 5000 subsamples (Temme et al., 2006). Figure 2 summarises the findings.

As to the research model's explanatory power, we can partly account for the main endogenous variables: intention to follow the recommendation ($R^2 = 0.716$), intention to purchase the recommended product/service ($R^2 = 0.671$) and intention to recommend the product/service ($R^2 = 0.551$). Based on Chin (1998), these findings suggest that the R2 values are substantial. In addition, the model explains more 70% of perceived usefulness and 3% of perceived credibility.

As to modality, voice recommendations had a direct, positive effect on credibility ($\beta = 0.259$, $p < 0.05$), but no direct effect on usefulness ($\beta = -0.017$, $p > 0.1$). This supports H1a, but not H1b. Perceived credibility had a strong, positive effect on perceived usefulness ($\beta = 0.838$, $p < 0.001$),

supporting H2. In addition, perceived credibility exerted positive effects on behavioural intentions to follow the recommendation ($\beta=0.525$, $p<0.001$), to purchase the recommended product/service ($\beta=0.495$, $p<0.001$) and to recommend the product/service ($\beta=0.346$, $p<0.001$). Thus, hypotheses H3a, H3b and H3c were supported. Similarly, perceived usefulness positively influenced intention to follow the recommendation ($\beta=0.354$, $p<0.001$), intention to purchase the recommended product/service ($\beta=0.357$, $p<0.01$) and intention to recommend the product/service ($\beta=0.427$, $p<0.001$), supporting H4a, H4b and H4c, respectively.

PLS-SEM was also used to analyse the moderating effect of product type on the influence of recommendation modality on credibility and usefulness. In line with the criteria proposed by Ringle et al. (2012) about dummy moderating variables, the present study used a two-stage approach, and followed the guidelines proposed by Cohen (1988) to perform the moderation analysis. H5 proposed that the difference between (a) perceived credibility and (b) perceived usefulness in terms of voice and text recommendations will be greater for experience products than for search products. However, the influence of the interaction term (consumer product type*modality) on credibility ($\beta=-0.330$, $t=1.008$, $p > 0.1$) and usefulness ($\beta=0.208$, $t=1.083$, $p>0.1$, respectively) was not significant. Thus, product type did not exert a moderating effect, thus H5 is not supported. On the other hand, product type exerted a direct influence on perceived credibility ($\beta=0.344$, $t=3.032$, $p < 0.01$) – that is, greater credibility is ascribed when the recommendation is about a search product– but no similar effect was seen with usefulness ($\beta=-0.042$, $t=0.560$, $p > 0.1$).

Figure 2. Structural analysis of the research model: Direct effects

Note: * $p<0.05$; ** $p<0.01$; *** $p<0.001$; ns: non-significant

Finally, the results showed that credibility may mediate the effects of recommendation modality on usefulness, and both credibility and usefulness may mediate the effects of

recommendation modality on behavioural intentions. Thus, we analysed these potentially mediated relationships by calculating the bias-corrected and accelerated confidence intervals of the effects (Chin, 2010; Zhao et al., 2010). The effects were shown to be significant when the intervals excluded the value 0. Table 5 shows the results of the mediation analysis. Although the direct effect of recommendation modality on usefulness was not significant, it has a positive, indirect effect via credibility. In addition, it was shown that recommendation modality exerts significant, positive indirect effects on intentions to follow the recommendation and to purchase the recommended product, and a marginal, indirect effect on intention to recommend the product, via perceived credibility and usefulness. Taking all the results into account, voice-based recommendations seem to create better perceptions and higher behavioural intentions than text-based recommendations.

Table 5. Total indirect effects

Effect	Mediator	Estimates	95% bias-corrected and accelerated confidence interval	t	P
Modality (Voice vs. Text) → Usefulness	Credibility	0.217	(0.021; 0.406)	2.192	<0.05
Modality (Voice vs. Text) → Intention to follow	Credibility & Usefulness	0.207	(0.005; 0.411)	2.004	<0.05
Modality (Voice vs. Text) → Intention to purchase	Credibility & Usefulness	0.199	(0.001; 0.395)	1.989	<0.05
Modality (Voice vs. Text) → Intention to recommend	Credibility & Usefulness	0.175	(-0.008; 0.356)	1.879	<0.1

4. STUDY 2

4.1 Methodology

4.1.1 Experimental design and measures

To improve the external validity and generalisability of the results, we conducted a second study to confirm that voice-based recommendations exert a greater influence on consumer behaviours than do text-based recommendations. Following Viglia et al. (2021) and Taylor et al. (2021), we presented participants with a situation in which they had to make choices, that is, whether to purchase a recommended product/service, and whether to recommend that product/service to other consumers. Thus, we aimed to examine the actual behaviours of participants towards the recommendations received.

This second study was also based on a between-subjects factorial experiment design. Specifically, a 2 (modality: voice vs. text) x 2 (product type: search vs. experience) x 2 (gender: male vs. female) factorial design was conducted. Thus, using the same modality and product type manipulations as in Study 1, we introduced gender as a control variable. Prior studies into online reviews have found that gender disclosure may affect consumers' perceptions of reviews (Ahn et al., 2022; Chevalier and Mayzlin, 2006), and even influence product sales (Duan and Whinston, 2008). For the voice assistant scenarios, we manipulated the voice (masculine vs. feminine) using the same software as in Study 1. For the online review scenarios, we included information about the reviewer and, using female and male names, indicated whether the reviewer was male or female. Thereafter, in an online survey the participants were asked to complete a questionnaire in which they made their behavioural choices as regards the recommendations, that is, whether or not to follow the recommendation, purchase the recommended product/service and to recommend the product/service.

The items addressing the actual behaviour of purchasing the recommended product/service were adapted from Viglia et al. (2021), Van Esch et al. (2021) and Mende et al. (2019), and the items for the actual behaviour of recommending the product/service were adapted from Viglia et al. (2021) and Basil et al. (2006) (see Appendix E). Again, we excluded responses that completed the questionnaire very quickly and/or failed the attention checks.

4.1.2 Manipulation checks

In this second study we checked whether the participants could identify gender (98% of participants confirmed the male gender condition, 100% confirmed the female gender condition), modality (99% of participants confirmed the text-based condition, 100% confirmed the voice-based condition) and product type (98% of participants confirmed the search product condition, and 97% confirmed the experience product condition; see Appendix F1). In addition, we controlled for realism, involvement and review characteristics (length, valence quality and brand familiarity of the reviewed product/service) using the same measures and scales as in Study 1. As to the realism scenario, there were no statistical differences in the means of user involvement, valence, length, quality of the recommendations and brand familiarity (FR=1.8, $p>0.1$; FI=2.46, $p>0.1$; FV=0.9, $p>0.1$; FL=1.44, $p>0.1$; FQ=1.24, $p>0.1$), indicating that the variables were homogeneous in all conditions (see Appendix F2).

Finally, we checked the answers to the questions about actual behaviours by posing an additional question about each of the consumers' decisions. On the one hand, to verify the choice made to purchase the recommended product, the participants were asked to decide whether to

purchase it, to look for other options or to keep the US\$85 they had been given. On the other hand, to verify the choice made to recommend the product, we included an open question where the participants had to describe exactly what they would tell their families, friends and acquaintances about the product. All the participants indicated they would recommend, and wrote positive things about, the product.

4.1.3 Data collection and estimation procedure

The data collection took place during July 2022. The data were collected through an online survey questionnaire with a sample of 401 US-based voice assistant users (at least 50 per scenario). Prolific, a market research firm, was enlisted to assist in the process. As in Study 1, in order to participate the candidates had to have used voice assistants at least once previously. Table 6 displays the sample's demographic characteristics, which are similar to those of Study 1. The nature of the dependent variables, actual behaviours, dictates measurement through a single dichotomous (purchase or not purchase; recommend or not recommend) indicator. Thus, we codified purchase behaviours as follows: 1= "Follow the recommendation and book the restaurant"; 0=otherwise. Similarly, recommendation behaviour was codified as follows: 1= "Yes, I would say something positive"; 0= Otherwise. Due to the dichotomous nature of the dependent measures, we conducted a logistic regression analysis (using SPSS v28 software) of the multivariate relationships between modality, gender, product type and the actual behaviours of purchasing and recommending the product/service. This is consistent with recent works using logistic regression method to analyse experimental data (e.g., Agarwal et al., 2022; Liu and Chou, 2020).

Table 6. Demographic characteristics of the sample

		Frequency	%
Gender	Male	198	49.4
	Female	193	48.1
	Prefer not to say	10	2.5
Age	18-30	177	44.1
	31-40	115	28.7
	41-50	47	11.7
	51-60	39	9.7
	Over 61	23	5.7
Education level	Graduate degree	78	19.5
	High/secondary school diploma	119	29.7
	Primary school diploma	4	1.0
	Undergraduate degree	200	49.9
Citizenship	USA	360	89.8
	Other	41	10.2

4.2 Results

Table 7 presents the results of the two logistic regressions, consumer choice (i.e., to purchase the product or not/recommend the product or not) being the dependent variable in each case. The findings of both logistic regressions show the effects of modality, gender and product type on both purchase and recommendation behaviours. Voice (vs. text) modality, male (vs. female) gender and search (vs. experience) products were positively associated with both behaviours. In other words, when the recommendation is about a search product, and provided by a male voice, there is a higher probability that people will purchase and recommend the product. Interestingly, these results are consistent with the results of Study 1, which suggested that voice-based recommendations and search products attracted more positive perceptions and behavioural intentions. Similarly, the influence of recommendation modality (voice vs. text) was higher and more significant for purchase decisions than for recommendation decisions. This is also in line with the results of Study 1, which suggested that recommendation modality has a slightly higher influence –indirect via credibility and usefulness– on purchase intentions than it has on recommendation intentions.

Table 7. Results of the logistic regression analysis

Independent variables	Dependent variables			
	To purchase: Yes/No		To recommend: Yes/No	
	β Coefficient	Odds ratios	β Coefficient	Odds ratios
Intercept	-1,847**	0,158	-0,313	0,731
Modality (<i>voice=1</i>)	0,468**	1,597	0,380*	1,463
Gender (<i>male=1</i>)	0,157*	1,170	0,409*	1,506
Product type (<i>search product=1</i>)	1,045***	2,844	0,311*	1,364

* <0.1 ** $p<0.01$ *** $p<0.001$ ns: non-significant.

5. DISCUSSION

The results of the two experimental studies contribute to the general body of knowledge about e-WOM and voice assistants. The test of the comprehensive research model: 1) explains the effectiveness of voice (vs. text) recommendations for predicting consumer behaviours; 2) compares in which context (search vs. experience products) these recommendations are more effective; and 3) confirms that credibility and usefulness are key factors in the explanation of the effectiveness of voice recommendations and of text-based recommendations.

The first study evaluated the influence of the modality of the recommendation (text vs. voice) on users' key perceptions (credibility, usefulness), which subsequently may affect behavioural intentions related to the recommendation (i.e., intention to follow the recommendation, intention to recommend and intention to purchase). In this respect, most of the proposed hypotheses were supported, and the key variables largely explained. The results confirmed that voice recommendations are perceived as more credible than text-based recommendations. These findings are consistent with the prior studies that suggested that voice messages transmit verbal, non-verbal and social cues which convey effectiveness and credibility (Perloff, 1993; Sproull and Kiesler, 1986). In turn, perceived credibility is a key determinant of the usefulness of recommendations. When recommendations are perceived as credible, they provide good information that is likely to help consumers predict how an experience will turn out, which enhances the usefulness of the information. This finding is in line with previous works on consumer decision-making, specifically in the context of traveller's generated content platforms

(e.g., Filieri, 2015) and social media platforms (Teng et al., 2014). In addition, the study results also suggested that voice (vs. text) recommendations influence usefulness via credibility. These findings are in line with previous research that supported the mediated role of credibility in predicting usefulness (Saima and Khan, 2020; McKnight and Kacmar, 2007).

The results also proved that both credibility and usefulness are key predictors of consumer behavioural intentions derived from recommendations. That is, the higher the credibility and usefulness of recommendations, the higher will be the consumer's intention to follow them, to make purchases and to recommend the product. Credibility and usefulness are widely studied consumer responses because of the impact they exert on product and brand evaluations (Craciun and Moore, 2019), and these effects have been confirmed by previous research in different contexts (e.g., Sussman and Siegal, 2003; Cheung et al., 2009; Filieri, 2015; Filieri et al., 2015). On the one hand, review credibility is an important determinant that affects whether consumers are persuaded by a reviewer's opinions, as consumers want to avoid being manipulated by biased online reviews (Grewal et al., 2019). On the other hand, useful recommendations help consumers make the right purchase decisions. In addition, when consumers consider information about a given product/service to be useful and credible, they are more likely to recommend that product/service to their contacts and other consumers looking for similar information.

As to whether the influence of voice (vs. text) recommendations is more important for search than for experience products, the study discovered no interaction effect of recommendation modality and product type on perceived credibility or usefulness. These findings provide interesting insights into the role of product type on the effect of recommendation modality on the credibility and usefulness of recommendations, confirming that the effect of voice modality does not change based on whether a product is search or experience. On the other hand, it seems to have a direct effect on credibility, with recommendations, in general, being perceived as more credible with search products. This finding may be explained by perceived stability theory. The attributes of search products are more stable and homogeneous than the attributes of experience products (Hsieh et al., 2005), so recommendations for search products may be attributed to real, stable factors and, consequently, be considered as more credible.

The second study presented participants with a situation in which they had to make choices (i.e., to purchase the product or not, to recommend the product or not) based on the recommendation's modality (voice vs. text), product type (search vs. experience), with the gender of the voice assistant being controlled (masculine vs. feminine voice). It was shown that voice (vs. text) modality positively influenced the consumer's choice to purchase and recommend

the product. This finding is in line with the communication clarity perspective (Grice, 1975), which suggests that the use of voice improves message clarity, helps listeners to focus on the ideas/proposals contained in the message and facilitates information exchange, which result in higher levels of effectiveness. In addition, this result is probably caused by the machine agent being perceived as human-like (e.g., possessing speaking/listening skills), as previous research has found that people develop more positive perceptions towards human-like robots (e.g., Eyssele and Hegel, 2012). Second, it was also seen that search products have a direct effect on both consumer choices, that is, whether or not to purchase and/or recommend. This is consistent with the results of the first study, as recommendations about search products are considered as more credible and may enhance purchasing and recommendation behaviours. Third, the results also showed that gender has a significant effect in predicting these consumer decisions. Focusing on voice recommendations, previous research has found that individuals are affected by gender stereotypes during their interactions with computers (Nass et al., 1997). While female voices may be perceived as warmer, and the industry trend is to use female rather than male voices (Tolmeijer et al., 2021), individuals perceive evaluations from computers with male voices as more valid than those from computers with female voices. This is especially important when consumers are judging a product's performance (e.g., suitcase/restaurant functions/performance, Ahn et al., 2022). This may be true in the context of the present study, as voice assistants are designed to offer individuals a useful and convenient way to search for product information/performance data (McLean and Osei-Frimpong, 2019).

5.1 Theoretical implications

This research makes four main theoretical contributions. First, it contributes to the voice assistant and e-WOM literature by taking a first step towards understanding the influence of the voice recommendations made by voice assistants on consumer behaviours, in comparison to the influence of text recommendations on consumer behaviours (i.e., online consumer reviews). While voice assistants are a relatively new phenomenon, which is attracting considerable interest from academics and practitioners, little is known about their potential to affect consumer behaviours.

Specifically, the present study analyses the role of voice assistants in the consumer decision-making process by empirically testing the causal connection between recommendation modality (voice vs. text) and consumers' perceptions of credibility and usefulness, which in turn influence consumers' behavioural intentions (to follow the recommendation, to purchase and to recommend the product/service). The results suggested that recommendations received from

voice assistants more strongly influence consumers' decisions than do text-based recommendations (e.g., online consumer reviews). By building a bridge between the literature on AI-based devices and e- WOM, this study highlights the power of voice technologies for increasing the effectiveness of product recommendations. Voice assistants can capture the consumer's preferences, humanise interactions, make recommendations more credible and useful, which leads to recommendation adoption.

Second, while previous researchers have applied MRT to organisational information (Daft and Lengel, 1986), emails (Schmitz and Fulk, 1991), websites (Patrakosol and Lee, 2013), mobile apps (Anandarajan et al., 2010) and social media (Xiao et al., 2021), the present study contributes to the MRT literature by applying it to an AI-based technology, voice assistants. More specifically, this research suggests that voice assistants are an AI-based technology able to interact using human-like cues (Chi et al., 2022). (Miller et al., 2013; Spence, 2019). Therefore, voice assistants can be regarded as a rich medium, as almost a face-to-face interpersonal interaction. Furthermore, the study contributes by supporting the proposal that the influence of E-WOM recommendations is affected by product type, that is, search vs experience (Park and Lee, 2009). We found no evidence of a moderating effect of product type on the influence of recommendation modality on credibility and usefulness; rather, this research found that recommendations about search products are perceived as more credible, and influence consumer decisions to a greater extent, than do recommendations about experience products.

Finally, the study showed that social psychology theory on gender stereotypes (in this context, that the perceived gender of a voice affects interpersonal conversations) can be applied to new domains, that is, we showed that gender voice affected AI-human interactions and consumers' behaviours based on voice assistants' recommendations. Although voice gender should continue to have an important influence in the design of voice assistants, little previous research has been undertaken in this field (e.g., Tolmeijer et al., 2021). In this respect, most virtual assistants convey gender-specific cues that can be classified as female (e.g., Feine et al., 2019). In turn, we found that male voices have greater influence on consumer behaviours, probably because of the research context. As stereotypical male (e.g., more assertive) and female (e.g., warmer) voices have different characteristics (Tolmeijer et al., 2021), their appropriateness may vary depending on the goals of the user-voice assistant interaction.

5.2 Practical implications

As aforementioned, the main contribution of this study is the finding that, due to their greater perceived credibility and usefulness, voice assistants' recommendations have a stronger, more

influential effect on consumer decision-making than do online consumer reviews (text-based recommendations). This finding highlights important points that should guide business managers (e.g., product managers, retail managers) and the designers of voice assistants.

The greater credibility ascribed to voice assistants' recommendations and its crucial role in shaping consumers' behaviours may lead product/retail managers to increase their use of voice technologies in their customer services and marketing communications (e.g., using voice assistants for launching/recommending new products). In addition, the research findings highlighted the important influence of perceived usefulness on consumer behaviours. Although voice assistant recommendations are perceived as more useful than online consumer reviews, practitioners should continue to focus on increasing the usefulness of the services provided by their virtual assistants. For example, supermarket/shop managers might think beyond the traditional role of voice assistants, that is, providing product recommendations, and use them to offer value-added services, such as providing recipes containing their brands, or even have them read out lists of ingredients to their users as they cook their food.

Furthermore, as the use of voice assistants proliferates, it becomes important for their designers to improve and innovate their voice technologies to increase the richness of the medium. With this aim, first, it is recommended they enhance their voice feature by introducing innovative technologies to convey human quirks (e.g., laughing, sneezing, sobbing) and carry fluctuations in tone when pronouncing words. Second, designers should develop new technologies to allow consumers to hold lengthy conversations. Designers, thus, should go beyond providing technologies that simply recommend, and develop means of offering near-human companionship throughout the purchase process. In addition, consumers tend to personalise their voice assistants when they give them useful recommendations (Cappellini, 2019). Therefore, it will become increasingly important for voice assistants to have personas and be more life-like. Furthermore, designers should solve accent and language problems by developing voice-enabled technologies that more readily recognise commands.

Finally, our findings suggest that practitioners should carefully consider the gender of voice assistants to ensure that they deliver the most effective and persuasive product recommendations. Specifically, and contrary to the industry mainstream, where most voice assistants are female (e.g., Feine et al., 2019), we found that a male voice was more influential. As aforementioned, masculine or feminine voices may be more appropriate based on the goal of the user-voice assistant interaction. Therefore, designers should not neglect male voices in voice assistant design. Similarly, our results suggested that voice assistants' recommendations are more

effective for search products. Therefore, managers of this product type should be aware of the influence that voice assistants exert on their consumers.

5.3 Limitations and further research

This research has limitations that open future research opportunities. First, the study focused on situational involvement, which is temporary in nature as it disappears when the purchase is completed (Bloch, 1981). Therefore, future works might take into consideration long-term product involvement to assess if consumers' perceptions of the importance of the product over time influence the relationships proposed in this research. In addition, the data were collected from voice assistant users based only in the United States; however, several research works have noted the importance of incorporating cultural differences when analysing AI-based technologies and consumer behaviours (Huang and Zhang, 2020). Thus, further studies might compare consumers' behaviours following AI-based voice assistant recommendations in different cultures, exploring, for example, potential differences between individualistic and collectivistic societies/countries. Finally, traditional psychology literature suggests that personality traits may significantly affect individuals' persuasion information processes (e.g., McCrae and Costa, 1987). Therefore, future research might examine how consumers' personality traits (e.g., the big five model) may affect their behavioural intentions towards voice assistants' recommendations.

6. CONCLUSIONS

To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first empirical research to investigate the effect of voice assistants' recommendations on consumer behaviours, by comparing both voice recommendations made by voice assistants, and text recommendations made in online consumer reviews. So to do, this research applied MRT (Daft and Lengel, 1986) and carried out two experimental studies focused on behavioural intentions (Study 1) and consumers' decisions (Study 2). The major finding of the study is that voice assistants' recommendations are more effective than online consumer reviews in directly –Study 2– and indirectly influencing (mediating credibility and usefulness) –Study 1– consumer behaviours. The results of Study 1 confirmed, in the voice recommendation context, the important role of credibility and usefulness in shaping consumer behaviours, previously demonstrated in the online consumer review context. The results of Study 2 also showed that voice recommendations are more effective when delivered by a masculine voice. Finally, both studies suggested that recommendations for search products are regarded as more credible and effective than recommendations for experience products. These findings provide practitioners with a rich understanding of voice assistant technologies which they can use to their advantage in their business strategies.

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Appendix A. Example of the text-based recommendation (search product)

Imagine you are traveling to meet your partner's parents for the first time. For you, it is a very important engagement and you want to impress your future in-laws as possible as you can. For this trip, you need to buy a new suitcase. As you need more information about suitcases, you decide to search some reviews written by other customers. In a social network, you come across this recommendation:

Appendix B. Example of the voice recommendation (experience product)

Imagine that you are looking for a restaurant to surprise your partner and invite her/him to a romantic dinner to celebrate your anniversary together. As you need more information about restaurants, you ask your voice assistant to read to you some recommendations based on other customers' choices, and you get the following recommendation:

Please click the following link to get the recommendation. Press play and listen the recommendation to the end:

<https://bit.ly/3Re181Z>

Appendix C1. Manipulation checks of the study 1 (pre-test)

Modality %		Product type%	
Voice	Text	Search product	Experience product
98	99	100	96

Appendix C2. Manipulation checks of the study 1 (pre-test)

	Realism	Involvement	Valence	Length	Quality	Brand familiarity
F	1.4	2.53	0.93	1.30	1.17	1.33
P-Value	0.21	0.15	0.48	0.25	0.32	0.41

Appendix D. Realism and involvement items

CONSTRUCT
Realism (adapted from Bagozzi et al., 2016)
REAL 1. How likely the scenario would be realistic
REAL2. I How likely the scenario would be believable
REAL3. How likely would you be to encounter a situation similar to the one described in the scenario.
Involvement (adapted from Zaichkowsky, 1985; Mather et al., 2016)
INVL1. Imagining the situation, I would be very interested in the purchase decision
INVL2. Imagining the situation, it would be important to me to make the right purchase decision
INVL 3. Imagining the situation, the purchase decision would mean a lot to me
INVL 4. Imagining the situation, the purchase decision would be relevant to me

Appendix E. Actual behavior items (Study 2)

ACTUAL BEHAVIOUR TO PURCHASE THE REVIEWED PRODUCT (adapted from Viglia et al., 2021; Van Esch et al., 2021; Mende et al., 2019)
Please, make a decision based on the aforementioned recommendation and indicate your choice among the following options:
Follow the recommendation and book the restaurant.
Search for more recommendations.
Do nothing.
Now, imagine that you have 85 dollars available, and you have to decide what to do based on the aforementioned recommendation:
I will follow the recommendation and book the restaurant
I will search for more recommendations
I won't follow the recommendation and keep the 85 dollars
ACTUAL BEHAVIOUR TO RECOMMEND THE RECOMMENDED PRODUCT (adapted from Viglia et al., 2021; Basil et al., 2006)
After reading the recommendation, would you tell your family, friends and your acquaintances, about the service:
Yes, I would say something positive
Yes, I would say something negative
Yes, I would say something neutral
I would say nothing
Please, write what would you exactly tell your family, friends and your acquaintances about the product: _____

Appendix F1. Manipulation checks of the study 2

Modality %		Product type%		Gender%	
Voice	Text	Search product	Experience product	Male	Female
98	99	100	96	98	100

Appendix F2. Manipulation checks of the study 2

	Realism	Involvement	Valence	Length	Quality	Brand familiarity
F	1.8	2.46	0.90	1.44	1.24	1.24
P-Value	0.33	0.12	0.45	0.20	0.42	0.56